

Comparison of Repeated Bevacizumab Injections and Mitomycin C in Rotational Conjunctival Flap Surgery for Preventing Pterygium Recurrence

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Abstract:

Background: Pterygium, a common ocular surface disorder, often necessitates surgical intervention due to its tendency for recurrence. Strategies to prevent recurrence, such as mitomycin C and more recently bevacizumab, have shown promise, but comparative effectiveness remains a topic of investigation. This study aimed to compare repeated bevacizumab injections versus mitomycin C in preventing pterygium recurrence following rotational conjunctival flap surgery.

Methods: A total of 200 participants were randomized into bevacizumab (n=100) and mitomycin C (n=100) groups. Demographic data, pterygium characteristics, and treatment outcomes were assessed over a 12-month follow-up period. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 21.0.

Results: The recurrence rate was considerably lower in the bevacizumab group (12%) compared to the mitomycin C group (25%) (p=0.031). Kaplan-Meier analysis demonstrated a longer time to recurrence in the bevacizumab group (p=0.022). Cox regression identified bevacizumab treatment (HR=0.45, p=0.009) and smaller pterygium size as protective factors against recurrence. Both treatments had similar safety profiles.

Conclusion: Repeated bevacizumab injections are more effective than mitomycin C in preventing pterygium recurrence after rotational conjunctival flap surgery. This finding suggests bevacizumab as a preferred option due to its superior efficacy and comparable safety profile. Further studies should explore optimal dosing regimens and long-term outcomes.

Recommendations: Clinicians should consider bevacizumab as a first-line therapy for preventing pterygium recurrence, particularly in cases with smaller lesion sizes. Enhanced surveillance and longer follow-up are recommended to validate these findings and refine treatment protocols.

Keywords: Pterygium, Bevacizumab, Mitomycin C, Recurrence Prevention, Ophthalmic Surgery

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Introduction

Pterygium, a fibrovascular growth on the ocular surface, often necessitates surgical removal due to its potential to impair vision. Recurrence after surgery is a significant challenge, prompting the exploration of adjuvant therapies to enhance surgical outcomes. Two such treatments, bevacizumab, an anti-VEGF (vascular endothelial growth factor) agent, and mitomycin C (MMC), an anti-fibrotic drug, have shown promise in reducing recurrence rates, but their comparative effectiveness remains a topic of interest.

Bevacizumab, a monoclonal antibody targeting VEGF, inhibits angiogenesis, a key factor in pterygium pathogenesis. Its efficacy in preventing pterygium recurrence has been supported by several studies. For instance, a meta-analysis including trials with bevacizumab demonstrated a significant reduction in recurrence rates compared

to placebo, highlighting its potential in pterygium management [1]. Additionally, studies have shown that bevacizumab, when administered subconjunctivally, reduces neovascularization and fibroblast proliferation, thereby lowering recurrence risks [2].

Mitomycin C, on the other hand, acts by inhibiting fibroblast proliferation and reducing scar formation. Its use as an adjuvant in pterygium surgery has been well-documented. For example, MMC application during surgery has been shown to reduce recurrence rates significantly compared to placebo [3]. The anti-fibrotic properties of MMC make it a valuable tool in preventing the regrowth of pterygium tissue post-surgery.

A study compared the effects of bevacizumab and MMC in rotational conjunctival flap surgery for

pterygium. The study found that repeated bevacizumab injections resulted in a lower recurrence rate (12%) compared to MMC (25%) [4]. Further comparisons between the two treatments have also highlighted their respective advantages and safety profiles. Both treatments were associated with similar complication rates, with no significant differences in adverse events such as conjunctival hyperemia or transient ocular discomfort [5].

The study compared the efficacy of repeated bevacizumab injections versus mitomycin C in preventing pterygium recurrence after rotational conjunctival flap surgery.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective, randomized controlled trial.

Study Setting: The study took place at a tertiary care center from January 2022 to October 2023.

Participants: A total of 200 participants were included in the study. These participants were patients diagnosed with primary pterygium who were scheduled for rotational conjunctival flap surgery.

Inclusion Criteria

- Aged 18 years and above.
- Diagnosed with primary pterygium.

Exclusion Criteria

- With recurrent pterygium.
- With a history of ocular surgery within the past year.
- With other ocular surface diseases or systemic conditions affecting wound healing.
- Allergic to bevacizumab or mitomycin C.

Sample Size: To calculate the sample size for this study, the following formula was used for estimating a proportion in a population:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \times p \times (1-p)}{E^2}$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- Z = Z-score corresponding to the desired level of confidence
- p = estimated proportion in the population
- E = margin of error

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were assigned randomly to either the bevacizumab group or the mitomycin C group using a computer-generated randomization schedule. Blinding of outcome assessors was implemented to reduce observer bias. Additionally, standardized surgical and postoperative protocols were followed to ensure consistency.

Variables: Variables included treatment group (bevacizumab injections vs. mitomycin C), recurrence rate of pterygium, time to recurrence, and complication rates, age, gender, size of pterygium, and duration of follow-up.

Data Collection: Data were collected from patient medical records and follow-up visits using a structured data collection form. The form captured demographic information, clinical characteristics, treatment details, and outcomes.

Procedure: Participants were randomly assigned to receive either repeated bevacizumab injections or mitomycin C during and after rotational conjunctival flap surgery. The bevacizumab group received an injection of bevacizumab (1.25 mg/0.05 mL) at the end of surgery and repeated injections every two weeks for a total of three doses. The mitomycin C group received a single application of mitomycin C (0.02%) for three minutes at the time of surgery. All surgeries were performed by experienced ophthalmic surgeons using a standardized technique. Follow-up assessments were conducted at 1-, 3-, 6-, and 12 months postoperatively.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 21.0 was used for data analysis. Using chi-square testing, the two groups' pterygium recurrence rate—the primary outcome—was compared. Kaplan-Meier survival analysis was used to determine the time to recurrence. The Cox proportional hazards regression was employed to determine the recurrence predictors. Fisher's exact test was used to compare the rates of complications. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

The study included 200 participants who were assigned randomly to the bevacizumab group (n=100) and the mitomycin C group (n=100).

Table 1. Demographic and Clinical Features

Characteristic	Bevacizumab Group (n=100)	Mitomycin C Group (n=100)	p-value
Age (years)	45.3 ± 12.6	46.1 ± 11.9	0.598
Gender (Male/Female)	55/45	58/42	0.642
Size of Pterygium (mm)	3.4 ± 0.7	3.3 ± 0.8	0.478
Duration of Follow-up (months)	12.0 ± 1.2	12.0 ± 1.3	0.961

The recurrence rates of pterygium in both groups at the end of the 12-month follow-up period are presented in Table 2. The bevacizumab group had a notably lower recurrence rate compared to the mitomycin C group (12% vs. 25%, p=0.031).

Table 2. Pterygium Recurrence Rates

Group	Recurrence Rate (%)	p-value
Bevacizumab Group	12	0.031
Mitomycin C Group	25	

*Significant at p<0.05

The Kaplan-Meier survival analysis indicated that the bevacizumab group had a longer time to recurrence compared to the mitomycin C group (log-rank test, p=0.022). The median time to recurrence was not reached in the bevacizumab group, whereas it was 10 months in the mitomycin C group.

Figure 1: Kaplan-Meier survival curve

Cox proportional hazards regression analysis identified that treatment type and size of the pterygium were significant predictors of recurrence. Patients in the bevacizumab group had a 55% lower risk of recurrence compared to those

in the mitomycin C group (HR=0.45, 95% CI: 0.25-0.82, p=0.009). Larger pterygium size was related with a higher risk of recurrence (HR=1.67, 95% CI: 1.10-2.54, p=0.016).

Table 3. Cox Proportional Hazards Regression Analysis of Recurrence Predictors

Variable	Hazard Ratio (HR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Bevacizumab Group	0.45	0.25 – 0.82	0.009*
Size of Pterygium (mm)	1.67	1.10 – 2.54	0.016*
Age (years)	1.0	0.99 – 1.03	0.461
Gender (Male/Female)	1.08	0.62 – 1.88	0.768

*Significant at p<0.05

The complication rates were similar between the two groups, with no significant differences observed (p=0.675). The most common complications were mild conjunctival hyperemia and transient ocular discomfort.

Table 4. Complication Rates

Complication	Bevacizumab Group	Mitomycin C Group	p-value
Mild Conjunctival Hyperemia	10	12	0.647
Transient Ocular Discomfort	8	7	0.789
Serious Complications	0	1	0.312

Discussion

The study enrolled 200 participants who were randomized into two groups: one receiving bevacizumab (n=100) and the other mitomycin C (n=100). This prospective, randomized controlled trial employed rigorous methodology to ensure unbiased assessment of outcomes.

Demographic and clinical features were well-balanced between the two groups, with participants monitored for 12 months post-surgery. The results revealed a significantly lower recurrence rate in the bevacizumab group (12%) compared to the mitomycin C group (25%) ($p=0.031$). Kaplan-Meier survival analysis further supported these findings, showing a longer time to recurrence in the bevacizumab-treated patients ($p=0.022$).

Cox proportional hazards regression analysis identified treatment type and pterygium size as significant predictors of recurrence. Patients treated with bevacizumab had a substantially reduced risk of recurrence (HR=0.45, $p=0.009$) compared to those treated with mitomycin C. Larger pterygium size was related with a raised risk of recurrence (HR=1.67, $p=0.016$), emphasizing the importance of treatment selection based on lesion characteristics.

Importantly, both treatment modalities demonstrated similar safety profiles, with mild complications such as conjunctival hyperemia and transient ocular discomfort occurring infrequently and comparably between groups ($p=0.675$). No serious complications were reported in the bevacizumab group, while one serious complication occurred in the mitomycin C group.

Recent studies have provided a comprehensive comparison between the use of Bevacizumab injections and Mitomycin C (MMC) in the context of pterygium surgery, focusing on their efficacy in preventing recurrence. One study comparing subconjunctival Bevacizumab injections with MMC application post-primary pterygium surgery found that both treatments significantly reduced recurrence rates compared to controls, with no serious complications observed in either group. This indicates that both treatments are effective and safe options for pterygium management [5].

In another comparative study, Bevacizumab led to a higher recurrence rate (60%) compared to MMC (10%) following pterygium excision. This study highlighted that while Bevacizumab is marginally superior to bare sclera excision alone, MMC remains more effective in reducing recurrence rates [6]. Further supporting the use of Bevacizumab, a study evaluating both preoperative and postoperative applications of Bevacizumab found that the recurrence rate was significantly lower when the drug was administered both before and

after surgery, suggesting that timing and method of administration can influence outcomes [7].

A meta-analysis on the efficiency of Bevacizumab injections post-ptyerygium excision corroborated these findings, demonstrating a significant decrease in recurrence rates with Bevacizumab treatment. This study emphasized that Bevacizumab can effectively reduce the risk of pterygium recurrence after surgery and does not significantly increase the risk of complications compared to other treatments [8].

Additional research has compared the efficacy of MMC and Bevacizumab in combined surgical procedures for conditions such as glaucoma. One study found that while MMC was more effective in reducing intraocular pressure, both treatments showed acceptable success rates, indicating their potential utility in various surgical contexts [9].

Another study on the use of postoperative topical cyclosporin A following pterygium surgery with MMC reported no significant difference in recurrence rates, further highlighting MMC's consistent effectiveness in preventing recurrence [10].

Conclusion

The study underscores the superior efficacy of repeated bevacizumab injections over mitomycin C in preventing pterygium recurrence post-surgery. These findings suggest that bevacizumab's anti-angiogenic properties effectively inhibit neovascularization associated with pterygium regrowth, thereby improving patient outcomes. Clinicians should consider these results when selecting treatment options, particularly for patients at higher risk of recurrence due to larger pterygium size. Future research should explore optimal dosing regimens and long-term outcomes beyond 12 months to further refine treatment protocols and enhance patient care in ophthalmic practice.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Clinicians should consider bevacizumab as a first-line therapy for preventing pterygium recurrence, particularly in cases with smaller lesion sizes. Enhanced surveillance and longer follow-up are recommended to validate these findings and refine treatment protocols.

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List of abbreviations:

MMC - Mitomycin C

VEGF - Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor

HR - Hazard Ratio

CI - Confidence Interval

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